

FORMING ELEMENTS OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BY USING TIMSS SAMPLE TASKS

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Abstract. The article contains suggestions and recommendations on the formation of elements of environmental education based on the TIMSS model tasks related to concrete and natural sciences for elementary school students.

Key words: environmental education, environmental activity, task, TIMSS, analytical tasks.

Environmental education, which is considered an important component of social education, not only enriches the ideas of nature and the environment among elementary school students, but also plays an important role in the full formation of knowledge, skills and abilities related to ecological activities. Formation of a conscious attitude to the environment and its problems in the young generation is the main goal of environmental education.

Environmental education among students is mainly formed on the basis of ecological knowledge, and they decide to have a reasonable and correct attitude towards nature. Implementation in ecological pre-school educational organizations, general education schools and further stages of education. Knowledge about the world of plants, creation of natural resources, ecology in our republic is summarized in the process of teaching subjects such as natural sciences, ecology, mathematics in secondary schools.

In the process of teaching mathematics in elementary schools of general education, it is possible to form the elements of environmental education based on the educational purpose of the lesson. As an example, we will give a sample of some tasks.

Task 1.

The graph shows the water level in a dam for 10 weeks. What was the water level for week 8?

Students determine that the water level in week 8 is 16 m using the graph of the change in the height of the water level by week. Students are given analytical information about the rational use of water resources and not wasting water.

Task 2.

The graph shows the amount of water in the tank leaking in 7 hours.

1. How many liters of water was in the container at first?
2. After 7 hours, the amount of water in the container was equal to how many liters?

3. After how many hours will the amount of water in the container be equal to half of the initial value?
4. The owner of the container paid a fine of \$1 for every 8 liters of water lost. How much is the fine after 4 hours?

Along with mathematical literacy, educational elements are inculcated in the mentioned issue. Educational aspects of using drinking water on the basis of economy are covered.

It is possible to recommend wide promotion of environmental education in problematic classes in public schools and to achieve the expected result:

- should include elements of environmental education as important components at all levels of education.
- the elements of environmental education should be reflected in science assignments.
- international assessment programs (TIMSS) that reflect the elements of environmental education should be regularly used in the course of the lesson.

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